

Development Strategy of Punti Kayu Tourism Forest in Palembang City, Indonesia; Willingness to Pay (WTP) Base Recommendation

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ABSTRACT: Punti Kayu is one of the natural tourism forests in Palembang City. Punti Kayu natural tourism forest is a conservation area with a development concept based on protecting the diversity of plant and animal species. Willingness to pay is one of the things that must be considered by tourism managers because the ticket price offered is unknown about the willingness to pay of tourists, there the researcher is interested in conducting this study to find out how satisfied visitors who visit Punti Kayu Nature Tourism and how willing tourists are to pay the ticket price if using the travel cost method. This study aims to (1) determine the level of satisfaction consisting of ticket prices, attractiveness, facilities and experience of visiting Punti Kayu and determine the comparison of satisfaction levels based on the area of origin, (2) determine the value of willingness to pay based on travel costs and determine the relationship between value. willingness to pay with the satisfaction level of visiting Punti Kayu, (3) knowing the formulation of Punti Kayu development strategy in Palembang City. The data processing method used was the calculation of the satisfaction level score, the willingness to pay analysis using the travel cost method and the development strategy analysis using the SWOT analysis. The satisfaction level of tourist visits who became respondents was 60 people and an average score of 3.51 with the satisfied category was 53.30 percent. The result of the analysis of willingness to pay the visit of Punti Kayu respondent based on the travel cost method is Rp30,196.36. Based on the results of the spearman correlation calculation, the sig. (2-tailed) is $0.01 < 0.05$, so there is the relationship between willingness to pay and the level of satisfaction. The results of the analysis of Punti Kayu's development strategy are in quadrant I formulation, namely the SO strategy with the strategy being to make several sports areas such as jogging track and make interesting photo spot such as adding a flower garden with an aesthetic impression.

KEYWORDS: Development strategy, Forest Tourism, Punti Kayu Forest, Willingness to pay.

INTRODUCTION

Forests are the majority source of biodiversity and ecosystem services, on which millions of livelihoods depend [1]. The Knowledge of willingness to pay (WTP) for recreation in the forest is needed by managers of public woods [2]. Lipton et al (1995) noted that economic value measurement of the maximum amount an individual is willing to forego in other goods and services to obtain some good, service, or state of the world, measurement of welfare is formally expressed in a concept called willingness-to-pay (WTP) [3]. Ecotraveler is nature, a conservationist. Ecotourism is a form of tourism that managed with a conservation approach. Supposed ecotourism is the management of the heart and culture of the community that guarantees sustainability and prosperity. At the same time, conservation is an effort to maintain the continuity of natural resources for the present and future (Fibrianto, 2021).

South Sumatra is one of the provinces in Indonesia, located in the southern part of the island of Sumatra. According to data from the South Sumatra Tourism and Culture Office (2019), this province in the five years from 2013 to 2018 recorded that the average growth of domestic tourists was 16.52 percent and foreign tourists 18.17 percent. Punti Kayu is one of the natural tourism forests in Palembang City. Punti Kayu natural tourism forest is a conservation area with a development concept based on protecting the diversity of plant and animal species. Punti Kayu natural tourism forest has the potential form of a pine forest panorama that has an attractive view. The relationship between tourism and the natural environment is an attraction for tourists and a place for the construction of tourist facilities. Some tourists want the atmosphere of the environment they visit to be a new atmosphere, meaning different from what they usually find every day. Efforts to understand the characteristics of tourists' desires and needs are important for tourism actors to know so that tourists can feel comfortable and satisfied when traveling.

The willingness of visitors to pay for the actual entrance ticket is the next factor to take into consideration, after the amount of visitor fulfillment and Punti Kayu's development. The desire to use Agrowista's facilities is one of the reasons why visitors are willing to

pay extra. In contrast, people who are unwilling to pay more believe that the cost of the entrance ticket is already costly and want to travel on a budget [5]. Willingness to pay is one of the things that must be considered by tourism managers because the ticket price offered is unknown about the willingness to pay of tourists, there the researcher is interested in conducting this study to find out how satisfied visitors who visit Punti Kayu Nature Tourism and how willing tourists are to pay the ticket price if using the travel cost method. Based on the description above, the author is interested in conducting a study entitled "Analysis of the Level of Tourist Visit Satisfaction and Development Strategy for Punti Kayu Forest Nature Tourism Park in Palembang City, to calculate the willingness to pay value based on travel costs and formulate development strategies that should be implemented by the manager of Punti Kayu Nature Tourism Park in Palembang City.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Willingness To Pay

Analysis of Willingness to Pay (WTP) of visitors to the Forest entrance charge is necessary to be used as a reference in measuring the Forest Entrance Ticket Price (HTM) in order to improve future management. The strategies used to compute the value of WTP are classified as parametric (logit model) or non-parametric (Turnbull method). The goal of utilizing two distinct approaches is to compare the maximum WTP value obtained (Rismawati & Fauzi, 2022). The WTP offered to workers in the tourism industry can assist in the sale of tourism-related items during periods of economic expansion. The contributions made by the wisatawans in the wisata area will develop a sense of belonging so they may participate in the existing environmental initiatives to support long-term development (Medida, 2021).

The decision made by the visitors during a tourism visit is an important one that should be carefully considered since poor facilities, maintenance, and safety in a particular tourism object can negatively affect the attendants' decision to enter a certain wisata object. The impact of environmental and societal factors can be felt in the willingness of workers to pay and the level of productivity they achieve. (Safa'atin, 2024). The method of estimating the economic value of the environment in the form of non-market benefits of an ecosystem as an environmental commodity that is not marketed, in the form of indirect use value or passive use of natural resources, including its beauty and existence, is known as the contingent valuation method (CVM) to determine willingness to pay (WTP) (Noviati Sadikin et al., 2017). In general, the findings from this review reveal that rural households in developing economies are willing contribute a significant amount of resources both in money and labor time for management and conservation of forest resources. The finding indicates that mean monetary amounts that households 'are willingness to pay for forest conservation in the developing countries ranges from \$0.01 to 85.09 (Abdeta, 2022).

Forest Tourism

Forest existence value varies from one individual to the other. Forest non-use value can be measured using a choice and/or stated preference in order to obtain people's willingness to pay to conserve the forest and other ecosystems, even though they may never use them directly (Bamwesigye et al., 2020). The estimated per trip value is comparatively small relative to estimates from other recreation studies but total consumer surplus is greater. The result implies that, due to ease of accessibility, the total value of recreation could be higher in forests close to urban areas (Dhakal et al., 2012). The importance of facilities for forest tourism to the development of forest tourism has been mentioned in many studies, but there is a lack of quantitative and specific research. In order to specifically study the effect of facilities for forest tourism on the development of forest tourism, a theoretical path from the cognition of the development level of facilities for forest tourism to the willingness of tourists to visit urban forest parks was constructed based on the perceived value theory (Zhang et al., 2022).

The amount of money spent on a tourist trip to Punti Kayu Tourist Park serves as the basis for calculating the economic value of tourism. These expenses consist of round-trip transportation (parking included), consumption, documentation, and other charges (such as zoo admission fees, game ride rentals, and tickets) (Subardin & Yusuf, 2011). The marketing of the forest tourism business from environmental management and protection perspective is an important issue to continue to be studied in many countries. This is because any business related to tourism should be a sustainable system in tourism governance, both local and foreign. Efforts to market tourism oriented towards sustainability and being profitable must be carried out so that each country's condition of forests and tourism can continue to be sustainable (Wurarah et al., 2022).

METHODS

The online survey method used in this study is an online questionnaire administered through Google Forms, which collects and organizes data for analysis. To analyze respondents' readiness to pay and their degree of satisfaction, this method is used to gather an overview, information about their characteristics, and travel expenses. Interviews with management, staff, and the Natural Resources Conservation Agency of South Sumatra Province yielded the Punti Kayu development strategy.

Sampling was done by purposive sampling by considering that the sample used as respondents had visited Punti Kayu at least once, while the sample used for the development strategy was seven people as a consideration, namely the management who knew the conditions of Punti Kayu.

The highest price stated by participants in the open-ended question with a possible scenario was their willingness to pay. The interquartile range and the median were used to summarize WTP. Owing to the non-normal distribution, the Mann-Whitney U test for two variables and the Kruskal-Wallis test for 2 variables were employed as nonparametric tests to compare the median data between participant groups. P value less than .05 was designated as the statistically significant level (Vo et al., 2021).

Adopting the Travel Cost Method (TCM) and the resulting steps for assessing the willingness to pay value (Damanik, 2018).

1. The zones are split up into multiple areas of origin, and the average distance from each to Punti Kayu is then determined.
2. Give examples, including travel expenses, the quantity of guests from each zone, the distance, the income, and the population of each zone.
3. The following formula is used to calculate the number of visits per 1000 in each zone (V).

$$V = \frac{V_i}{n} N \times 52 \times 1000$$

Description:

V_i = Number of visitors from zone i n = Number of samples (people)

N = Visitors per week (people) P = Number of residents in zone i

The estimated total travel cost is obtained by adding the travel cost to the opportunity cost conversion value. The opportunity cost conversion value is obtained by multiplying the average travel time per zone by the wage conversion per minute. To find out the wage conversion value per minute, first find out the applicable minimum wages in 2020. Here is the formula for finding the wage conversion value per minute:

$$\text{Wage conversion per minute} = \frac{\text{Minimum Wages in 2020}}{8 \text{ hours} \times 26 \text{ days}}$$

Estimate the level of visits per 1000 residents in each zone with total travel costs using the following regression equation formula

$$V = a - b \cdot TC$$

$$b = \frac{\sum XY - n \bar{X} \bar{Y}}{\sum (X^2) - n (\bar{X})^2}$$

$$a = \bar{Y} - b \bar{X}$$

X = Total travel cost or TC (Rp/ Visit)

Y = Visit rate per 1000 residents

V = Visit demand equation per 1000 residents

Create a demand curve using a linear regression equation between the level of visits per 1000 residents per year and the total cost of travel for each zone. Calculate the total value of benefits and the average willingness to pay for maximum visits using the benefit value. The following is the formula for finding the benefit value and the average willingness to pay.

Benefit value = Total Benefit value – (valid tickets x visit rate)

$$\text{Willingness to pay} = \frac{\text{Benefit value}}{\text{Number of requests for visits at various alternative rates}}$$

The third objective in the analysis using SWOT analysis is to minimize weaknesses and threats and use strengths to take advantage of opportunities. The internal and external data obtained will be grouped to determine the factors that are strengths and opportunities, but at the same time can minimize weaknesses and threats.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Number of tourist visits to punti kayu

Punti Kayu Nature Tourism Park (TWA) is one of Palembang City's protection areas. It was formerly a 50 hectare experimental pine area. The Punti Kayu forest area was designated as a tourist forest that serves as the city's lungs on March 17, 1985, by force of the Decree of the Minister of Forestry Number 57/Kpts – II/1985 (Subardin & Yusuf, 2011). Punti Kayu is a conservation forest area used for air tourism, hiking trails, fishing, photography, sports, nature tourism, and raising swamp animals, among other tourism and leisure activities. Punti Kayu has been visited by domestic and foreign tourists for recreational purposes.

The increase of the number of visits per year from 2009 to 2020 experienced a decrease and increase in the number of visitors. In 2010, it had the highest number of visits, namely 204,334 tourists compared to other years, while in 2020 it experienced a drastic decrease of 2,129 tourists. This is because in 2020 from mid-March to early August Punti Kayu was closed due to the Covid-19 pandemic. Tourists who became respondents were counted as having visited Punti Kayu at least once. The number of visits was divided into several types, namely once, twice, three times and more than three visits to Punti Kayu. The number of tourist visits that were the most frequent respondents was 46.67 percent, while 5.00 percent were for the number of visits more than three times. This shows that the tourists who were the respondents predominantly only visited Punti Kayu once.

Punti Kayu Tourist Travel Costs

The travel costs of Punti Kayu tourists consist of several types of costs, including transportation costs, entrance tickets, consumption, tickets per ride, parking and so on. Tourists to visit Punti Kayu mostly use private transportation such as motorbikes and cars so that fuel costs are the largest cost in traveling compared to other costs. Tourists who use public transportation such as buses, online motorcycle taxis and LRT are grouped into costs in the form of fares. To find out the fuel costs, researchers assume that based on the average use of fuel and the type of motor vehicle used, it is premium at a price of IDR 7,850 per liter. One liter of fuel can cover a distance of 50 km for motorbikes and 15 km for cars, so the fuel per km is IDR 157 for motorbikes and IDR 523 for cars and the fuel costs are calculated twice for going back and forth.

The cost of Punti Kayu tourist travel consists of several types of costs including transportation costs, entrance tickets, consumption, tickets per ride, parking and so on. Tourists to visit Punti Kayu mostly use private transportation such as motorbikes and cars so that fuel costs are the largest cost in traveling compared to other costs. Tourists who use public transportation such as buses, online motorcycle taxis and LRT are grouped into costs in the form of fares. To find out the fuel costs, researchers assume that based on the average use of fuel and the type of motor vehicle used, it is premium at a price of IDR 7,850 per liter. One liter of fuel can cover a distance of 50 km for motorbikes and 15 km for cars, so the fuel per km is IDR 157 for motorbikes and IDR 523 for cars and the fuel costs are calculated twice for the return trip. Table 1 below is a breakdown of each respondent's travel costs to Punti Kayu.

Table 1. Details of respondents' travel costs to Punti Kayu

No	Travel cost	Cost (Rp)	Percentage (%)
1	Round trip fare	505.000	7,07
2	Round trip fuel costs	3.459.068	48,44
3	Entrance ticket	692.000	9,69
4	Consumption cost	1.030.000	14,42
5	Tourist attraction fees	720.000	10,08
6	Parking cost	305.000	4,27
7	Another cost	430.000	6,02
	Amount	7.141.068	100,00

Willingness to Pay Analysis Using Travel Cost Method

Willingness to pay analysis can be known by the travel cost method. The following are the steps of the analysis of willingness to pay for Pundi Kayu tourist visits in sequence.

Division of Zones

The division of zones is done by dividing based on the number of regions of origin in South Sumatra. Based on the results of the study, the number of regencies/cities that were respondents in the study was 12. The division of zones into 12 can be seen in the following table.

Table 2. Zone division

No	Zone	Average distance (Km)
1	Palembang	7,78
2	Ogan Ilir	37,80
3	Banyuasin	14,14
4	Musi Banyuasin	135,00
5	Muara Enim	185,00
6	Kabupaten Pali	138,00
7	Ogan Komering Ilir	113,00
8	OKU Timur	182,33
9	Lahat	226,25
10	Prabumulih	92,80
11	Lubuk Linggau	306,00
12	Pagaralam	286,50

Based on Table 2. The average distance from the area of origin to Pundi Kayu with the division of zones into 12 ranges from 7.78 to 306 km. The average closest distance is respondents from Palembang and the furthest from Lubuk Linggau. This analysis is identified based on the division of zones and then the average distance of each area to Pundi Kayu is calculated. The next step is to calculate the total travel cost. The distance calculation is carried out using the help of Google Maps, to find the average distance per zone, namely by dividing the total distance by the number of respondents per zone. The average distance data per zone is then used to calculate the opportunity cost conversion value to calculate the willingness to pay for Pundi Kayu tourist visits.

Determining Visit Level

The next step is to find out the population of each zone (P) which is divided into 12 regencies or cities using primary data according to the Central Statistics Agency in 2020. This population will be used to calculate the next step. The population can be seen in the following table. The rate of visits per 1000 from each zone can be calculated by knowing the number of visitors to Pundi Kayu each week by using data on the number of visits in 2020, namely 2,129 tourists. Visits are then divided by 52 so the number of visitors each week (N) is 41. The number of respondents (n) is 60 people. The following is a table of the number of respondents from each zone (Vi). In this study, the rate of visits per 1000 each zone can use the following formula (Damanik, 2018).

$$V = \frac{\frac{V_i}{n} N \times 52 \times 1000}{P}$$

The visit rate per 1000 from each zone can be calculated by knowing the number of respondents from each zone (V_i) in Table 3.

Table 3. The visit rate per 1000 from each zone

No	Zone	The visit rate per 1000
1	Palembang	0,38
2	Ogan Ilir	0,43
3	Banyuasin	0,30
4	Musi Banyuasin	0,23
5	Muara Enim	0,29
6	Kabupaten Pali	0,19
7	Ogan Komering Ilir	0,22
8	OKU Timur	0,16
9	Lahat	0,35
10	Prabumulih	0,97
11	Lubuk Linggau	0,16
12	Pagaralam	0,52
Amount		4,20

Estimating Total Travel Costs

Based on the results of the study on travel costs per visit obtained from the sum of the costs of transportation, return fuel, entrance tickets, costs per ride, parking, food and other costs, the results of the travel costs per visit were obtained from the average travel costs from each of the 12 zones.

Table 4. Estimated total travel cost

No	Zone	Respondent (People)	Total travel costs (Rp)	Travel Cost (Rp)
1	Palembang	18	1.159.388	64.410,44
2	Ogan Ilir	5	414.794	82.958,80
3	Banyuasin	7	399.662	57.094,57
4	Musi Banyuasin	4	519.768	129.942,00
5	Muara Enim	5	997.176	199.435,20
6	Kabupaten Pali	1	108.332	108.332,00
7	Ogan Komering Ilir	5	484.096	96.819,20

8	OKU Timur	3	732.162	244.054,00
9	Lahat	4	728.638	182.159,50
10	Prabumulih	5	607.728	121.545,60
11	Lubuk Linggau	1	370.076	370.076,00
12	Pagaralam	2	619.248	309.624,00
Amount		60	7.141.068	1.966.451,32

In this study, the total travel cost is obtained based on the sum of travel costs with the conversion value of the opportunity cost of travel time. The conversion value of the opportunity cost of travel time is obtained by calculating the average time required by converting it into a monetary value using the applicable wage rate. In 2020, the minimum wage based on PP No. 78 of 2015 was IDR 3,043,111.00 per month assuming the applicable working hours are 8 hours per day, one month 26 days so that the conversion of the wage rate is IDR 244 per minute.

Table 5. Total Travel Costs

No	Zone	Visit rate/1000	Average travel time/minute	Opportunity cost conversion of travel time (Rp)	Travel Cost (Rp)	Total Travel Cost (Rp)
1	Palembang	0,38	19,78	4.825,78	64.410,44	69.236,22
2	Ogan Ilir	0,43	77,40	18.885,60	82.958,80	101.844,40
3	Banyuasin	0,30	28,71	7.006,29	57.094,57	64.100,86
4	Musi Banyuasin	0,23	216,00	52.704,00	129.942,80	182.646,00
5	Muara Enim	0,29	198,80	48.507,20	199.435,20	247.942,40
6	Kabupaten Pali	0,19	198,00	48.312,00	108.332,00	156.644,00
7	Ogan Komering Ilir	0,22	156,40	38.161,60	96.819,20	134.980,80
8	OKU Timur	0,16	236,00	57.584,00	244.054,00	301.638,00
9	Lahat	0,35	299,75	73.139,00	182.159,50	255.298,50
10	Prabumulih	0,97	127,00	30.988,00	121.545,60	152.533,60

11	Lubuk Linggau	0,16	439,00	107.116,00	370.076,00	477.192,00
12	Pagaralam	0,52	397,00	96.868,00	309.624,00	406.192,00
Amount		4,20	2393,84	584.097,00	1.966.451,32	2.550.548,78

Based on the results of the addition between travel costs and the conversion of opportunity costs of travel time, the lowest total travel cost is the total travel cost in the Banyuasin zone, which is IDR 64,100.86 per visit and the highest is the Lubuk Linggau zone with a total travel cost of IDR 477,192.00 per visit.

Aggressive Visit Rate Per 1000 Population

The relationship between the total cost of travel in each zone and the level of visits per 1000 residents per year is a function of demand for visits to Punt Kayu. The following is a regression calculation between the level of total travel costs and the level of visits per 1000 residents.

Table 6. Regression calculation between total travel costs and the number of visits per 100 residents

No	Zone	Population (people)	Total cost of the trip (X)	Visit Rate (1000) (Y)	XY	X ²
1	Palembang	1.662.893	69.236,22	0.38	26.630,39	4.793.654.467,60
2	Ogan Ilir	419.773	101.844,40	0.43	43.105,10	10.372.281.811,36
3	Banyuasin	833.625	64.100,86	0.30	19.126,13	4.108.919.886,45
4	Musi Banyuasin	629.791	182.646,00	0.23	41.220,16	33.359.561.316,00
5	Muara Enim	618.762	247.942,40	0.29	71.192,32	61.475.433.717,76
6	Kabupaten Pali	184.671	156.644,00	0.19	30.140,54	24.537.342.736,00
7	Ogan Komering Ilir	809.203	134.980,80	0.22	29.636,06	18.219.816.368,64
8	OKU Timur	663.481	301.638,00	0.16	48.463,50	90.985.483.044,00
9	Lahat	401.494	255.298,50	0.35	90.378,50	65.177.324.102,25
10	Prabumulih	182.128	152.533,60	0.97	148.797,20	23.266.499.128,96
11	Lubuk Linggau	226.002	477.192,00	0.16	75.026,87	227.712.204.864,00
12	Pagaralam	.136.605	406.492,00	0.52	211.41,26	165.235.747.064,00
Amount		6.768.428	2.550.549,79	4.20	835.188,02	729.244.267.507,02
Average		564.035	212.545,73	0.35	69.599,00	60.770.355.625,59

Based on the calculation results in the table above, the next step is to carry out calculations using the following equation function formula.

$$b = \frac{\sum XY - n \bar{X} \bar{Y}}{\sum (X^2) - n (\bar{X})^2}$$

$$b = \frac{835.188,02 - (12 \times 212.545,73 \times 0,35)}{729.244.267.507,02 - (12 \times 45.175.688.027,23)}$$

$$b = - 0,00000030579$$

$$a = Y - bX$$

$$a = 0,35 - (- 0,00000030579) (212.545,73)$$

$$a = 0,41$$

Based on the calculation, the values of a and b are obtained and then substituted into the equation. V is the level of visits per 1000 residents and TC is the total cost of travel. The following is the equation that will be used in calculating the demand for visits per 1000 residents at the specified rate.

$$V = 0,41 - 0,00000030579 TC$$

Creating a Demand Curve

The demand curve can be calculated using the previously calculated demand function between the total travel cost and the number of visits per 1000 residents in each zone. This calculation is used to determine the demand for visitors to Pundi Kayu with various alternative rates determined. The greater the alternative rates, the less the demand for visitors to Pundi Kayu will be until there are no more visits at the specified rate. Based on additional calculations, various entrance ticket rates can indicate the demand for the number of visits to Pundi Kayu.

Additional various rates and number of visit requests are used to determine the total value of Pundi Kayu benefits. The results of the calculation of the total benefit value can be seen in the attachment. The following is an example of how to calculate visit requests if the entrance fee is added to the Palembang zone. If the entrance fee is IDR 10,000, the total cost of the trip is IDR 69,236.22 + IDR 10,000.00.

$$V_{\text{Palembang}} = 0,41 - 0,00000030579 (79.236,22) = 0,34$$

Total visits to the Palembang zone if the entrance fee is IDR 10,000 , then:

$$0,39 \times 1.662.893 = \frac{649.621.000}{1000}$$

Based on the calculation of the total benefit value of the Pundi Kayu visit of Rp. 964,450,284.86. The total benefit value is used to determine the benefit value of Pundi Kayu. The following is the calculation for the benefit value.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Benefit value} &= \text{Total benefit value} - (\text{valid entry ticket} \times \text{visit level}) \\ &= \text{Rp}964.450.284,86 - (\text{Rp}10.000 \times 2.44,47) \\ &= \text{Rp}964.450.284,86 - \text{Rp}24.474.694,30 \\ &= \text{Rp}939.97.590,56 \end{aligned}$$

Based on the results of previous calculations, it is known that the number of requests for visits at various rates is 31,128.77, so the average willingness to pay value obtained is as follows.

$$\text{Willingness to pay} = \frac{\text{Benefit Value}}{\text{Number of requests for visits to various alternative rates}}$$

$$\text{Willingness to pay} = \frac{\text{Rp}939.975.590,56}{2.447,47}$$

$$\text{Willingness to pay} = \text{Rp}30.196,36 \text{ per visit}$$

Willingness to pay = IDR 30,196.36 per visit Based on the calculation results, it can be seen that the average value of willingness to pay for maximum visits using the travel cost method is IDR 30,196.36 per visit

CONCLUSION AND GENERALIZATION

Based on the discussion above, conclusions can be drawn as follows, The level of satisfaction of tourists visiting Punti Kayu consisting of price, attraction, facilities and visiting experience. The level of satisfaction with the attraction received the satisfied category with an average score of 3.95. The overall satisfaction level was obtained at 53.30 percent who said they were satisfied. Tourists who visit Punti Kayu based on their area of origin from Palembang City and its surroundings and other than Palembang City and its surroundings, there is no difference in satisfaction levels. Analysis of the willingness to pay for visits by Punti Kayu tourists based on the travel cost method obtained an average calculation result of IDR 30,196.36

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